

CHARACTERISTICS OF ECONOMIC LITERATURE AND IT’S TRANSLATION

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Abstract. *The research is focused on the currently rapidly developing field of translation of economic terms, in which terminology construction, translation of economic terms in specific texts, and problems in the translation of economic terms are studied. It describes how to find the equivalents of the currently widely used terms in 3 languages, and how to translate them into English, Uzbek, and Russian languages if the equivalents of the phrases are not found.*

Keywords: *economic literature, translation strategies, economic development.*

Chapter I. Introduction

When science and technology are developing all over the world, the emphasis on learning foreign languages is growing day by day. Learning of foreign languages is not only for philologists, but for all professions. It is very important for the representatives because of learning of at least 2-3 foreign languages in the XXI century has become the essential requirement of the time. In modern Uzbekistan, in addition to Uzbek, learning English and Russian is a great help in the field of specialization and in the field expands the study of achievements. There is a need for representatives to learning foreign languages when signing an economic agreement with another country or establishing various diplomatic and international relations.

It is known that the economy plays an important role in any society. Therefore, words and terms related to economics should be clear, concise and logical. The rapid development of science and technology also affects the economy. As a result, a number of other economies will be affected leads to the emergence of new neologisms in the field.

In general, international economic words are widely used in Uzbek aspects need to be considered. When the economic term enters the Uzbek language it is necessary to pay attention to the following aspects: The Uzbek language of the term compatibility with the sound system; whether it has an Uzbek alternative; the content of the economic term; it’s simple and fluency; to the essence and convenience.

The term is derived from Latin (*terminus* - border, had) refers to a specific area of knowledge or activity a word or phrase that expresses a concept. The term is popular language passes through a certain terminological system, hence the term and common words are complementary lexical units.

Chapter II. General concepts about terms

2.1 English terminology and their construction

The economic development of the country depends on various factors. One of the most important factors contributing to economic development is the large number of industries that produce quality products or provide quality services. A developed country is expected to contribute to the rapid development of services and industry. Therefore, the development of industry and economic development are interrelated. The translation industry, especially business and technical translation services, has grown rapidly in recent years. Especially in countries where new business networks are opening up in the market every day and as a result of globalization there are great opportunities for growth.

Local markets are also full of foreign products, and many foreign countries provide services to these local markets. In a developed economy, cross-border trade was expected to be not limited to goods and services. On the contrary, it involves a large amount of cultural exchange. This exchange is directly related to economic development. After all, economic development means more cultural exchange. Translation services play an important role in bridging the gap between the two countries, thus facilitating the exchange of literature, knowledge, services and products.

In the process of this ongoing transformation, the translation industry has become a major necessity, especially in the market economy. It was motivated to acquire learning and skills and to adapt them to what they had academically. In other words, in today's globalized world, translation has become an integral part of such economic growth. The translation industry allows factories to better understand what is happening in Europe and around the world.

The term refers to a profession that has a professional meaning and the relationship between individual objects is a word used in the process of knowing and mastering accumulation. Because the word of each industry only applies within that range. More precisely, the profession shapes the owner's speech, as well as the conditions for mutual verbal communication creates. Professionals are often deal with specific terms relating to that field. For example, in the speeches of future economists: cartel, clearing, trade, money are terms used only in the field of economics. However, there are a number of terms in the field of economics that are specific almost all language possessors can be used equally in speech. Market, sales, buyer, traders, speculators, and so on.

Economic terms are somewhat different from common words. The economic term does not arise spontaneously, but it is possible will be discovered according to the function. The economic term does not have multiple meanings. The word can be used in several senses. Economic terms of the Uzbek language depend on different sectors of the economy. They can be removed based on specializations:

1. **Banking:** national currency, sum, value, price, coupon, savings, treasury, banknotes, promissory notes, checks, credit cards, money circulation, money mass, monetary aggregate, banking, monetary system, metallic theory, quantitative theory, money supply, inflation, credit, commercial credit, bank credit, government credit, international credit, credit limits, leasing, account credit, leasing operations, lease agreement, credit mechanism, loan amount, interest rate, credit risk, assets, liabilities, interest margins, export credit, problem loan.

2. **Taxes and taxation:** tax object, tax sources, tax rate, tax unit, tax rate, tax return, tax policy, tax mechanism, tax system, direct tax, indirect tax, customs duty, state duty, rent fee, payment, profit tax, advance payments, profit, gross profit, corporate income, taxpayer, value added tax, excise tax, land tax, property tax, population tax, tax office, tax committee, tax law.

3. **Finance:** financial function, financial policy, financial theory, finance control, financial resource, financial relationship, economic relationship, property attitude, state budget, depreciation allowances, depreciation fund, work salary fund, incentive fund, distribution, regulation, pension fund, employment fund, financial plan, income and expense balance, business plan, planning, business entity, charity fund, gross domestic product, etc.

In general, economic words and terms last a long time are lexemes. It is well known that the economy plays an important role in any society. As a result, economic terms are clear, concise, and logical should be appropriate. The issue of nationality and internationalism in

Uzbek economic terminology is a complex issue because it is not only in Uzbek but also in other languages not sufficiently resolved.

Chapter III. Methods of translating economic terms

3.1 Translation of economic terms in scientific texts

There are many ways to enrich terminological systems, the most important one is the word formation. In spite of word formation or how to use them, word formation of new words is necessary. On the role of new word formation in linguistics by V.V.Vinogradov the thought expressed is exemplary. According to him, the term is important in linguistics lexicology is the study of the lexical structure of a language. As they approach grammar - the doctrine of form and word is also related to the syntax of the compound. The number of supporters of this view is growing day by day.

As we consider the formation of new words, we will look at the typology of languages in this area just as the similarities are obvious, so too are their differences. As a confirmation of this opinion on five Slavic languages (V.A. Nikonov 1962, pp. 103-116) and three Germanic languages, the results of research conducted on (V.V.Gurevich 1970) can be cited.

English and Russian are Indo-European languages it is natural for a new word to have many similar features. However, the above-mentioned the relationship of separate word-formation among tools has different characteristics. The formation of a unique word the existence of methods and the ways in which words are formed in each language is characterized by individuality, which is manifested by the degree of productivity.

Affixation is the process of making a word by adding word-forming devices to the core. Affixes There are three types of word formation: using suffixes, prefixes using suffixes and prefixes. Also without affixes and words you can also create a word by adding.

1. Terminology using suffixes: In the field of economics, in general -er, -r, -ment, -ist suffixes in the construction of professional neologisms is effective:

Import + **er** = Importer - Import qiluvchi , Импортёр

Insure + **r** = Insurer – Sug'urtachi – Страховщик

Rent + **er** = Renter – Ijarachi – Арендатор

Pay + **ment** = Payment – To'lov – Платеж

Special + **ist** = Specialist – Mutaxassis – Специалист

Some professional term created in this way have led to the internationalization going on:

For example: Auditor – Auditor – Аудитор

Banker – Banker – Банкир

Broker –Broker (dallol) – Брокер

Dealer – Diler (sotuvchi) – Дилер

Investor Investor (pul bilan ta'minlovchi shaxs)

Manager – Menejer – Менеджер

2. Word formation using prefixes: The term is formed by adding prefixes, in this way neologisms not so common:

Ensure – Kafolat berish – Гарантировать

Income – Daromad – Доход

Inloading – Yuk tushirish – Разгрузка

Prepayment – Muddatdan oldingi to'lov – Досрочный платёж

3. Word formation with using suffixes-prefixes:

In this type of word formation, the prefix is at the same time the base also creates a new word by adding suffixes:

Illiquidity – Likvid yo`qligi – Отсутствие ликвидности

Incorporated – Uyushma, birlashma sifatida ro`uxatga olingan, tasdiqlangan –
Зарегистрированный как Корпорация

Indebtedness – Qarzdorlik, qarz summasi – Задолженность; сумма Долга

Outstanding – To`lov qarzlari – Неоплаченные счета

Overpricing – Narxlarning oshirilishi – Завышение цена

Underestimated price – Pasaytirilgan narx – Заниженная цена

The most English neologisms in a similar field of economics and some of them are even becoming international. For example, if we consider terms "businessman", "business + man" and "businesswoman" these terms are composed in the form of "noun + noun" components. In the construction of these neologisms in English, gender is also distinct. In Uzbek language also pays attention to this process.

3.2 Problems encountered in the translation of economic terms in scientific texts

It is necessary to translate various district documents into other languages when establishing relations between countries. Differences in the semantic systems of different languages are an indisputable fact is the source of the difficulties. The following problems occur during the translation process.

1. Lexical problem: Units in the translated language (foreign language lexicon) lack of alternatives.

2. Stylistic problem: Except for neutral words, only within certain specific genres the presence of certain words and phrases used.

3. Grammar problem: In another foreign language of grammatical means absence.

The existence of peoples in different natural, economic, socio-political conditions as a result of their consciousness, worldview and various special concepts and norms, principles are decided, all of which are reflected in language. But concepts that have emerged in another country in the development of technical progress meaning that neologisms do not have an alternative in another language possible.

Because every living language is constantly changing and evolving. His one of the moving components is the dictionary. To other language fronts rather than its expansion through lexical big dynamics and above all change and development.

Vocabulary with an alternative is a language of such a word or phrase representing things, processes and beings that appear in the stages of development are words which do not have an alternative in translation. It has an alternative option graduation as the basis of non-verbal vocabulary was the basis of our professional work an example is "economic terms". If alternative is not found in the translation of economic texts in Uzbek, there methods for solving this issue:

1. Transcription.

2. Transliteration

3. Calque

4. Descriptive expression.

I. Transcription.

Phonetics of Uzbek and English languages due to the important difference of the system, such a signal is a condition and a working out some similarities and differences of how many English sounds produces. In general, transliteration is definitely necessary when an interpreter uses transcription elements cannot be bypassed. Seeing it all, transliteration in general and transcription elements are reflected in the following.

1. Transliteration of unpronounced sounds.

2. Transliteration of reduced flours.

3. Transliteration of double consonants.

4. Some of the available options, is the closest to the graph.

Agency – Agentlik – Агентство , Antique – Antik,(qadimiy narsa) – Аантиквариат , Auditor – Auditor – Ааудитор , Audit – Audit (taftish) – Аудит (ревизия), Attestation – Attestatsiya – Ааттестация , Cargo (cargo ensurance) – Kargo (yukni sug'urtalash) – Карго(страхование груза) , Clause – Klauzula– (qonun, shartnoma, vasiyatnoma qismi, sharti, tanbehi) – Клаузула (условие, оговорка, пункт закона , договора, завещания), Consignor – Konsignant (dallollar orqali chegaradan o'tadigan tovarlarning egasi) – Консигнант (владелец то-вара, продаваемого за границу через посредников.)

II. Transliteration.

The reason it is so named is in the translation movement instead of sound motion or the edge being translated when using the methods, the content of words in the native language is given by giving a graphic form will come. The method of transliteration is the formation of an English word with Uzbek letters is a method of giving letters.

For example: “Dotatsiya” – Dotation – Дотация. Organization, state aid to enterprises, extra charge. Mainly for damages and other purposes used.

“Diler” – Dealer – Дилер. By stock exchange or trading intermediation at its own expense engaged businessman.

III. Calque

Calque of the shield does not change the internal shape. Calqueis right between the two languages to the lexical units of the elements present in the internally reciprocal languages relies on: superpower - сверхдержава- hukumron davlat ; mass culture - массовая культура – ommaviy madaniyat; green revolution - зеленая революция-yashil revolutsiya ; transnational - транснациональный – transmilliy.

Auction - (lat.auction)- «kim oshdi» savdosi. During this trade, the product is purchased by the consumer at the highest price.

Demping - (ing.dumping-tashlash)- market capture and selling products with lower price than the selling price in order to get rid of them.

3.3 Analysis of economic term in newspaper materials

In the current transition to a market economy, we are in the newspaper texts it is natural that we encounter economic terms. In particular, some economic terms in the newspaper "Uzbekistan Today" there are some examples from it.

Tashkent Institute of Finance held a seminar for students on the initiative of the Uzbekinvest, a national export-import insurance company.

Ташкентский финансовый институт провел семинар для студентов по инициативе Узбекинвест, национальной экспортно-импортной страховой компанией.

Toshkent Moliya Instituti talabalarga milliy export-import sug'urta kompaniyasi o'zbek investitsiyasining tashabbuskorligi haqida seminar o'tkazdi.

A type of linguistic transformation in translating this term we use the method of Kalkalash, which is the original lexicon involves the replacement of a unit with a lexical unit in the target language. Translation leads to the formation of a new word or phrase in the language:

The word Uzbekinvest is new by adding the word Uzbek to the word "investitsiya" and "o'zbek investitsiyasi" is emerging.

Here are some terms from an article in the **British Financial Times**:

The wide range of services, such as loans and insurance packages, causes some difficulties for the consumer to make the right choice.

Широкий спектр услуг, таких как кредиты и страховые пакеты, вызывает определенные трудности для потребителей, чтобы сделать правильный выбор.

Xizmatlarning keng ko'lamdaligi , qarzlar va sug'urta yuklari kabilar iste'molchiga to'g'ri tanlovda ayrim qiyinchiliklarga sabab bo'lmoqda.

We translate the term Loans as "Qarzlar" why these "loans" is not translated "debt" because the word loans fit the context perfectly the word "debt" has another meaning, such as "duty-burch".

In the newspaper "**Uzbekistan Today**" the term of "business" is internationalized and used the transliteration method of linguistic transformation:

Small business and entrepreneurship development has become a source of employment for the majority of individuals who previously worked in industry and collective agriculture.

Малый бизнес и развитие предпринимательства стала Источником занятости для большинства людей, которые ранее работали в промышленности и коллективного сельского хозяйства.

Kichik beznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik rivojlanishi ko'pchilik kishilarga ya'ni avvaldan sanoat va qishloq xo'jaligida ishlaganlarga xizmat manbai bo'lib qoldi.

The national press is the face of society. Because it is just the latest news, events are not only reflected, but also the globalization of society process is also reflected. The fact is that the accuracy of the opinion expressed, the editorial staff is high to be spiritual, broad-minded and to serve the people whole heartedly they are convinced that they are noble people who aspire.

Conclusion

The rapid development of science and technology also affects the economy. This will result in a number of other economies leads to the emergence of new words in the field. Synonymy in all terminology work considered as a serious shortcoming the market economy has so far developed that it has no alternative the experience of states shows.

Now among the people to the market economy, especially entrepreneurship and its interest in the forms is great. The Republic of Uzbekistan is a similar development has chosen his path and is walking boldly from it. It should be noted that this is the economy ultimately lies in serving human interests. His goal strengthening the social aspects of the economy, the consumer of production to submit to the demands of the people to achieve the well-being of the

population through abundance by creating a free business environment in the country diligence. Business acumen, thrift, the value of time is to reshape qualities such as maturity.

Moreover, these would mean that you have to spend for these processes the international terms used in the Uzbek language are also unique assimilation. It is important to note that this newcomer that it is difficult to find an Uzbek alternative to all the terms. That is why the most of them have their own form in the languages of most countries of the world is used in its original form, and this application is used by business people around the world to exchange information convenient for.

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